

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, mart.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI TIZIMLASHTIRILGAN TAHDIDLAR.....	40
Qodirov Tuyg'un Uzoqovich, Nabiyev Bexzod Shavkatovich	
SANOAT TARMOQLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSIYA VA TEXNOLOGIK MODERNIZATSIYANING O'RNI	44
Boboqulov Sanjar Bahromqulovich	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIYOTI VA UNING SOLIQ TIZIMIDA QO'LLANILISHI	49
To'xtabayev Oybek Odilovich	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH BO'YICHA ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR.....	56
Ismailov Bobir Salomovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY JIHATLARI	62
Yangiboyev F.B.	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY SALOHİYATDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	68
Turayev Og'abek Kaxramonovich	
XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAJRIBASI.....	75
Yusupova Feruza Yo'ldoshevna	
BANK XIZMATLARI SIFATINI BOSHQARISHNING INTEGRATSION VA ADAPTIV MODEL.....	83
Ibroximov Ilxomjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLAR ASOSIDA BAHOLASH	89
Qidirniyazov Ajiniyaz Sherniyazovich	
ICHKI NAZORAT VA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDAGI XAVFLARNI BOSHQARISH	94
Islamova Nargiza Mirzaxidovna	
TURIZMNING MINTAQADA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI	104
Rasulova Muxabbat Teshabayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH ORQALI INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING HOZIRGI KUNDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	111
Begamov S.X.	
RETHINKING JOB CREATION: ONTOLOGICAL AND EPISTEMOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MACROECONOMIC EMPLOYMENT ANALYSIS.....	116
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
HUDUDIY TURIZM KLASTERLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA ULARNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	125
Ro'zimova Xusnora Mirzobek qizi	
SUG'URTACHILIK VA O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA SEKTORINING HOLATI.....	129
O'runboyeva Sotima Alisher qizi	
GO'SHT VA GO'SHT MAHSULOTLARINI SANOAT USULIDA QAYTA ISHLASHDA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBALARI.....	134
Kaydarova Sitora Suranbay qizi	
KORXONALAR QIYMATINI BAHOLASH VA BOZOR BAHOSINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	139
Abduraxmanov Sherzodbek Ravshanovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIK VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK UYG'UNLIGI.....	145
Jamaldinova Asalxon Saliyevna	
2025-YILDA O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN ENG YAXSHI 10 TA TRANSPORT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA INNOVATSIYALARI	151
Mamasaliyeva Mukaddas Ibadullayevna, Beketov Timur Kazakbayevich	

MAHSULOT TANNARXINI ANIQLASHNING INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN YONDASHUVLARI: AN'ANAVIY VA ZAMONAVIY TIZIMLAR QIYOSIY TAHLILI	155
Tulyaganov Abdumalik Abdiraximovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННО-ИНВЕСТИЦИОННАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ В НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПОДХОДОВ	163
Хайдарова Ёркиной Аскар кизи	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INNOVATSION TADBIRKORLIKNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING FISKAL VA INSTITUTSIONAL MEKANIZMLARI	170
Mamatova Nodira Mirzavaliyevna	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА И УСТОЙЧИВЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ МОДЕЛИ ПЕРЕХОДА ТЕПЛИЧНЫХ ХОЗЯЙСТВ ТАШКЕНТСКОЙ АГЛОМЕРАЦИИ НА СОЛНЕЧНЫЕ СИСТЕМЫ ЭНЕРГОСНАБЖЕНИЯ	178
Срджиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна, Абдувалиева Зилола Абдуллаевна	
МАМЛАКАТИМИЗДА QISHLOQ HUDUDLARIDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	186
Yuldashova Nilufar Ziyabayevna	
RIVOJLANISHDA RAQOBAT EMAS, BALKI HAMKORLIKNING USTUVORLIGI: NAZARIY VA AMALIY TAHLIL	190
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich	
IJTIMOY HIMOYA QAMROVINI KENGAYTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI VA "QAMRAB OLINMAGAN O'RTA QATLAM" MUAMMOSI	196
Bafoev Farrux Jo'raqulovich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA EKOLOGIK BOSHQARUVNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	202
Shanazarova Gulyoraxon Baxtiyarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON STARTAP EKOTIZIMIDA INVESTITSIYA JALB QILISH JARAYONINING INSTITUTSIONAL MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH MEKANIZMLARI	208
Xoliqova Xurshidaxon Xayotjon qizi	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA STARTAP EKOTIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHLTLARI	214
Usmanov Gafurjon Shavkatovich	
QURILISHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA SIFATNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHI	220
Buriyev Xakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ilxom Achilovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSION MUHITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING STRATEGIYALARI	225
Xolov Sherali Axrorboyevich	
2010-2024-YILLARDA O'ZBEKISTONDA TO'QIMACHILIKNI INVESTITSIYALASHNING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI	229
Ashurov Shuhratbek Qudrat o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI	233
Sherbekova Kamola Norbekovna	
AHOLI MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGI DARAJASI VA UNI BAHOLASHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	243
Abduvoxidov Akmal Abdulazizovich	
MARKAZIY BANK KURS SIYOSATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI	249
Saydullayev Nodirbek Narzullaevich	
O'ZBEKISTON MINTAQALARIDA BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SALOHİYATI VA MUAMMOLARI	258
Raupov Shuxrat Soyibovich	
ЭКОТУРИЗМ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ	264
Абидова Дилфуза Игамбердиевна, Рахматуллаева Зулайхо Хасан кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: BUSINESS CHANGE IN THE REGIONS	270
Abdullayev Muzaffar Abdujabbarovich	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIK MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLASHDA IOT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	273
Mirzaev Dilshod Artikovich	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ СТАРТАП-ПРОЕКТОВ В ВУЗАХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	279
Касимова Наргиза Сабитджановна	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	284
Ismoyilova Mahliyo Oybek qizi	
BOSHQARUVDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR (OLIV TA'LIM MISOLIDA).....	289
Kariyeva Gulnora Abdullayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV MIJOZLARGA XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI VA ASOSIY TENDENSIYALARI.....	295
Qurbonov Odilbek Ro'zmatovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SPORT FEDERATSIYALARI VA ASSOTSIATSIYALARINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'LLARI.....	302
Umed Farmonkulovich Radjabov	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA QARATILGAN IQTISODIY MEKANIZMNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ULARNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI.....	307
Mullayeva Mexrangiz Axtam qizi	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'LLARI (NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	313
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Muradova Nazira Raximjanovna	
RAQAMLI MARKETING VA ONLAYN PLATFORMALAR ORQALI EKOTURISTIK MAJMUALARNI OMMALASHTIRISH TRENDI.....	318
Xolmatova Parvina Asliddin qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGI STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI VA ULARNI YECHIMLAR.....	323
Normurzayev Umid Xolmurzayevich	
РАЗВИТИЕ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО БАНКОВСКОГО ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ В ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ НА ОСНОВЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА КАК ФАКТОР РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	327
Бахтиёров Худайберган Хамдам угли	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLARDA TRANSFERTLARGA QARAMLIK DARAJASINI BAHOLASH (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	335
Xudoyqulov Hamidjon Abdullayevich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI.....	342
Tajibaev Berdax Asqarbay uli	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI JADALLASHTIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	347
Ashurova Maftuna Ortiq qizi	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING CAPITAL EFFICIENCY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS: DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT INTEGRATION.....	352
Sadullaeva Mokhinur Aziz kizi	
TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT AND SME INTERNATIONALIZATION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW.....	358
Abduxafizova Madinabonu Mirabbos qizi	
TA'LIM SIFATINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH USULLARI.....	363
Mamadiyarov Zokir Toshmurovich	
SMART UNIVERSITET KONSEPSIYASI ASOSIDA REYTING VA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI INTEGRAL BOSHQARISH.....	371
Xudoyqulov Husen Ahadovich	

BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING MILLIY VA XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOT 1-SHAKLINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI	379
Shodiyev Murodjon Bakirovich	
SUG'URTA BOZORINING RAQAMLI RIVOJLANISHIDA NAZARIY QARASHLAR	384
G'oziyeva Aziza Abdusalomovna	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA INNOVATSION LOYIHALAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI	389
Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLAR DAROMADLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	397
P.SH.Usmonov	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА МЕТОДОВ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОГО АНАЛИЗА ДЛЯ ОЦЕНКИ ДОХОДНОСТИ АКЦИЙ УЗБЕКСКИХ ЭМИТЕНТОВ.....	401
Ирмухамедова Муслима Дилшодовна	
KORXONA VA TASHKILOTLARDA INSON KAPITALIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHDA KORPORATIV MADANIYAT, AXLOQIY-RUHIY VA MA'NAVIY MUHITNING O'RNI	407
Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmurodovich, Qodirov Tuyg'un Uzoqovich	
ELEKTRON PULLARNING MOHIYATI VA ULARNING MILLIY TO'LOV TIZIMIDAGI ROLI.....	416
Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA UY XO'JALIKLARINING TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KENGAYTIRISH.....	423
Eshbaeva Shahnoza Faxriddinovna	
APPLICATION OF EXTREME MODELS IN ASSESSING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF AN ENTERPRISE	428
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGIDA XORIJIY TAJRIBA HAMDA UNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH SAMARADORLIGI.....	435
Bozorova Ozoda Raximovna	
DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATI IMIJINI OSHIRISHDAGI MUAMMOLARNI HAL ETISHDA XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI: QIYOSIY TAHLIL.....	439
Bekmurodov Navruz Ergashevich	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI SOHASIDA YARATILGAN YALPI QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT DINAMIKASI VA UNI BOSHQARISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	449
O'rinov Komiljon Kozimovich	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHNING MINTAQAVIY OMILLARI.....	453
Salomat Norova	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI BOZORI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	459
Usubjonov Zaxriddin Vasliddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA EKSPORT OPERATSIYALARINI SUG'URTA QILISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	465
Xalikov R. B.	
BIZNES JARAYONLAR AUTSORSINGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH USULLARI TAHLILI	472
Uzaqov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
DAVLAT MOLIVAVIY BOSHQARUVI SAMARADORLIGINING IJTIMOY ADOLATGA TA'SIRINING PEFA VA CEQ METODOLOGIYALARI ORQALI TAHLILI	477
Zokirjonov Muhammadsodiq Ravshanbek o'g'li	
NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA ICHKI AUDIT XIZMATINI TASHKIL QILISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	485
Turmanqulov Norpo'lat Sa'dullayevich	
MINTAQADA IJTIMOY HIMOYA TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH.....	491
Saparov Ismat Chorshanbiyevich	
MINTAQANI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDA EKOLOGIK INNOVATSIYALARNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH YO'NALISHLARI	495
Ismatov Sharofiddin Asatulloevich	

THE ESSENCE OF THE OPTIMAL COST STRATEGY	500
Sodiqov Mirakhror Abbos ugli	
TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TOG'-KURORT ZONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY JIHATLARI (CHORVOQ ERKIN TURISTIK ZONASI MISOLIDA)	504
Shomurodova Shahnoza G'ayratovna	
ICHKI AUDIT SIFATI VA SAMARADORLIGI TUSHUNCHALARINING IQTISODIY MAZMUNI HAMDA ULARNING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGI	509
Ergashev Olloyor Furqat o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARI FAOLIYATINI SOLIQQA TORTISH VA UNI HISOBINI YURITISH.....	517
Abdullayev Abdurauf	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING RISKLARINI BAHOLASHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	522
Kudaybergenova Guzal Kuanishbayevna	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORRUPSIYAVIY-KOMPLAENS MUAMMOLARI: TAHLIL VA YECHIMLAR.....	527
Yunusov Baxtiyor Shavkatovich	
MAISHIY XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNING SIFAT NAZORATINI HAMDA TASHKILIIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	532
Meliyev X.T.	
ОЦЕНКА КАЧЕСТВА СЕРВИСА И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ НА ОСНОВЕ СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОПРОСА.....	541
Усманова Азиза Баходировна	
RAQAMLI BANK XIZMATLARI ORQALI MOLIVAVIY INKLYUZIVLIKNI KENGAYTIRISH.....	545
Azlarova Mushtariybegim Abror qizi	
QURILISH KORXONALARNI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI	550
Egamov Raxmatillo Mirolimovich, Bobobekov Davron Gafurovich	
FINANCIAL MARKET PARTICIPANTS: A CLASSIFICATION BY ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITY.....	553
Khotamkulova Madina	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ «ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ МАХАЛЛИ» КАК ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНОГО МЕХАНИЗМА РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В СФЕРЕ ГОСТЕВЫХ ДОМОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	559
Иргашева Нигина Салохиддиновна	
BANKLARDA KREDIT GAROVI BILAN ISHLASHNING XORIJ ILG'OR TAJRIBASI VA UNDAN O'ZBEKISTON BANKLARI AMALIYOTIDA FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	567
Sh. Saidov	
MILLIY UGLEROD SAVDOSI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	573
Islamov Shoxzod Shuxrat o'g'li	
THE NECESSITY OF CREATING A BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT AND ITS ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	582
Amanov Davron Ravshan ugli	
SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI	588
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Mahammatov Hoshim, Esanbekov Diyorbek	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЁТА БАНКОВ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО И ПРИНЦИПАМИ ESG.....	595
Насирдинов Шарифджон Изатуллоевич	
ОЦЕНКА ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОБУСА.....	600
Мухитдинов Акмал Анварович, Касимов Омил Камалович, Саидов Азамат Илхом угли	
XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR ASOSIDA DUKKAKLI DON MAHSULOTLARINI YETISHTIRISHNI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH YO'NALISHLARI (HINDISTON TAJRIBASI MISOLIDA).....	608
Mirsayd Xudaybergenov	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLINING FAROVONLIGI VA DAROMAD MANBALARINI STATISTIK TAHLILI	612
Mamatkulov Baxtiyor Xalmuradovich	

KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	618
<i>Muxamedjanova Maxfuza Baxodir qizi</i>	
MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARNING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI, MAZMUNI HAMDA KLASSIFIKATSIYASI.....	627
<i>Odiljonova Oybarchin Fayzullo qizi</i>	
XALQARO MOLIYA INSTITUTLARI ORQALI MAMLAKATIMIZ LOYIHALARINI AMALGA OSHIRISH TARTIBI TAHLILI.....	631
<i>Rasulova Dilfuza Valiyevna</i>	
HUDUDNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA IQTISODIY SALOHİYATNING O'RNI	636
<i>Avazbek Xalbekov</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SABZAVOTCHILIK TARMOG'INING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	642
<i>Sobir Xasanov</i>	
IMPACT OF REGIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND NATURAL RESOURCE UTILIZATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL TOURISM (A DISTRICT-LEVEL ANALYSIS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION, UZBEKISTAN)	650
<i>Toyirova Shohista Bobobekovna</i>	
INNOVASION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY OMILLARI	657
<i>Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna</i>	
BOZOR BEQARORLIGI SHAROITIDA BANK OBRO'SINI STRATEGIK RESURS SIFATIDA BARQARORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	661
<i>Yuldasheva Kamola Qosimjonovna, Ziyeva Muhtasar Mansurdjanovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT PENSIYA TIZIMINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	667
<i>Pardayev Farrux Muzaffarovich</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMASIYA SHAROITIDA MENEJERLARNING RAQAMLI KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	671
<i>Sharipova Zulfiya Shokirjonovna</i>	
FUQAROLAR ISHTIROKIGA ASOSLANGAN TASHABBUSLI BUDJETLASHTIRISH TIZIMI VA UNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	677
<i>Shukurova Parizod, Soatova Nodira Boboxonovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ HUDUDLARINING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARIDA QISHLOQ TURIZMI VA EKOTURIZM – ASOSIY USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	682
<i>Abduraxmanova Aqida Fayzulla qizi</i>	
KORXONALARDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLARNING SHAFFOFLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING ROLI	691
<i>Alimbay Shamshetov</i>	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA YASHIL INVESTITSIYALARNING MOLIYAVIY MEXANIZMLARI	694
<i>Saule Ibragimova</i>	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF ELECTRICITY GENERATION BY WIND POWER PLANTS.....	698
<i>Saidov Mash'al Samadovich</i>	
TRANSFORMING TOURISM EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: AN INSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS OF PERSONNEL TRAINING SYSTEMS.....	706
<i>Abdullakhujaev Abdukodirkhuja, Ochilova Hilola Farmonovna</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	713
<i>Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich</i>	
MAHALLIY BOSHQARUVDA YETAKCHILIK KONSEPSIYASI ORQALI FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH (FARG'ONA VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	718
<i>Siddikov Abdusalom Abdumalikovich</i>	

NEW ECONOMIC PHENOMENA: FINANCING CONSUMPTION AND SAVINGS IN THE TRANSITION TO AN EXPECTATION ECONOMY.....	724
Isomov Bekmurod Sayfiddinovich	
XIZMAT KO'TSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK YO'NALISHIDA INSTITUTSIONAL O'ZGARISHLARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING OBYEKTIV ZARURIYATI.....	730
Sh.A.Sultonov	
MINTAQALARNING INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLARI VA ULARNING IJTIMOİY-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	737
Qobilov Anvar Eshpo'latovich	
KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	741
Madraimova Marxamat Raximberganovna	
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТУРИСТСКО-РЕКРЕАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНА.....	748
Усманова Зумрад Исламовна	
TITLE: PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP AS A MECHANISM FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN.....	753
Suxrobbek M. Salayev	
XORAZM VILOYATI TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATIDAGI TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNI BAHOLASH VA UNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	761
Urunov Farrux Shanazarovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT AUDITI TIZIMINING STRATEGIK TRANSFORMATSIYASI: INSTITUTSIONAL ISLOHOTLAR VA RAQAMLI MONITORINGNING STRATEGIK AHAMIYATI.....	765
Turabov Baxodir To'xtamishovich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA BANDLIKNING 2025-2030-YILLARDAGI PROGNOZ PARAMETRLARI.....	770
N.I. Shermamatova	
BO'SH TURGAN DAVLAT KO'CHMAS MULK OBYEKTLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNI TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATLI JIHATLARI (O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA).....	776
Sanjarov Zuxriddin Dilshod o'g'li, Astonaqulov Muzaffar Muxsin o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING RESURS BAZASI BARQARORLIGINI TAVSIFLOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR.....	781
Bolibekov Shahboz Baxodir o'g'li	
MOLIYA-KREDIT JARAYONLARI: INVESTITSION FAOLLIKNI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMI SIFATIDA.....	787
Madaminov In'omjon Ozodovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	792
Karimov Islombek Bekpo'lat o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIMDA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI SAMARADORLIGI.....	798
Uzaydullayev Sherzod Shukurullayevich	
XUSUSIY MAKTABLARNING BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI QAROR QABUL TIZIMLARI VA O'RGANUVCHI ANALITIKASI YORDAMIDA YANGILASHNING YO'LLARI	802
Esanova Shohida	
MOLIYA BOZORIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ISLOMIY MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	812
Abduraxmanova Matluba Maxamadaminovna	
KORXONALARDA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'LLARI	819
Mirzaev Ozod Furkatovich	
ЛЕКСИЧЕСКАЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ КОМПОНЕНТ ПРОДУКТИВНОЙ ПИСЬМЕННОЙ РЕЧИ.....	824
Киличева Феруза Бешимовна	
MODERN MECHANISMS FOR MONITORING REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL ECONOMY	828
Karimova Shirin Zokhid qizi	

АЛЬТЕРНАТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ КРЕДИТНОГО СКОРИНГА ДЛЯ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ БЕЗ БАНКОВСКОЙ ИСТОРИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	833
Шухратова Мадинабону Икром кизи	
SHAHAR EKOLOGIYASI: SHAHAR EKOTIZIMLARI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH	841
Erkiniva Mukarram Olimjon qizi	
CHAKANA SAVDO XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATUVCHI KORXONALARDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	845
Abdug'aniyev Oybek Akmaljon o'g'li	
KUZATUV KENGASHI XUSUSIYATLARINING KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI: NAZARIY VA KONSEPTUAL YONDASHUV.....	850
Jumayeva Go'zal Sherxon qizi	
EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH NATIJALARI NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISHDA MUHIM AMALIY AHAMIYAT.....	854
Sattorov Firdavs Ziyodullayevich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIJORAT BANKLARINING O'RNI.....	858
Abduholikov Kamoldin Mahammadjonovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING HUDUDLAR KESIMIDAGI RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARINI STATISTIK TAHLIL QILISH.....	862
Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA XIZMATLAR EKSPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING EKOLOGIK JIHATLARI.....	867
Qodirjonov Adxamjon Muxtorjon o'g'li	
INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNI MOLIALASHTIRISHNING XALQARO MODELLARI VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGI.....	872
Muxamedjanova Dilshodxon Muzaffarovna	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA "YASHIL" TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONINING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	877
Ismatulloeva Madinabonu Fozil qizi	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI MAHSULOTLARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASH	884
Kadirova L.G.	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REGION	887
Nasretdinova Farangis Odilovna	
THE IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS IN THE SERVICES SECTOR	895
Mamatkulova Shoira Djalolovna	

THE IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS IN THE SERVICES SECTOR

Mamatkulova Shoira Djalolovna

Candidate of Economic Sciences,
Associate Professor of the Marketing department,
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract. In this article, we examine the role and importance of marketing communications in the development of the service sector in the modern economy. Particular attention is paid to the impact of integrated marketing communications on developing competitive advantages for service companies, increasing customer loyalty, and improving service quality. We analyze the main tools of communications policy, including advertising, public relations, digital marketing, and direct communications with consumers. Based on this analysis, we propose areas for improving marketing communications aimed at enhancing the performance of service sector organizations.

Key words: marketing communications, service sector, digital marketing, competitiveness, customer loyalty, integrated communications, advertising, pr, customer experience, crm systems.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada biz zamonaviy iqtisodiyotda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda marketing kommunikatsiyalarining roli va ahamiyatini o'rganamiz. Xizmat ko'rsatish kompaniyalari uchun raqobatbardosh ustunliklarni rivojlantirish, mijozlar sadoqatini oshirish va xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini yaxshilashga integratsiyalashgan marketing kommunikatsiyalarining ta'siriga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Biz reklama, jamoatchilik bilan aloqalar, raqamli marketing va iste'molchilar bilan to'g'ridan-to'g'ri aloqalarni o'z ichiga olgan kommunikatsiya siyosatining asosiy vositalarini tahlil qilamiz. Ushbu tahlil asosida biz xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi tashkilotlarining faoliyatini yaxshilashga qaratilgan marketing kommunikatsiyalarini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlarini taklif qilamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: marketing kommunikatsiyalari, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, raqamli marketing, raqobatbardoshlik, mijozlar sadoqati, integratsiyalashgan kommunikatsiyalar, reklama, PR, mijozlar tajribasi, crm tizimlari.

Аннотация. В данной статье мы рассматриваем роль и значение маркетинговых коммуникаций в развитии сектора услуг в условиях современной экономики. Особое внимание уделяется влиянию интегрированных маркетинговых коммуникаций на формирование конкурентных преимуществ предприятий сферы услуг, повышение уровня лояльности клиентов и улучшение качества обслуживания. Мы анализируем основные инструменты коммуникационной политики, включая рекламу, связи с общественностью, цифровой маркетинг и прямые коммуникации с потребителями. На основе проведенного анализа предлагаются направления совершенствования маркетинговых коммуникаций, направленные на повышение эффективности деятельности организаций сферы услуг.

Ключевые слова: маркетинговые коммуникации, сектор услуг, цифровой маркетинг, конкурентоспособность, лояльность клиентов, интегрированные коммуникации, реклама, PR, клиентский опыт, CRM-системы.

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized and competitive environment, the service sector is increasingly playing a significant role in the national economy. The growing share of services in gross domestic product, the development of digital technologies, and changing consumer preferences necessitate improved management and promotion methods. In this context, the effective use of marketing communications as a key tool for engaging with consumers and building sustainable competitive advantages is particularly important. Marketing communications play a crucial role in educating consumers about the services offered, fostering a positive company image, and stimulating demand. Unlike the commodity market, services are characterized by intangibility, variable quality, and the inability to store them, significantly complicating their promotion. Therefore, service companies require more flexible and comprehensive communications strategies focused on establishing long-term relationships with customers.

Current trends in the digitalization of the economy are contributing to the transformation of traditional approaches to marketing communications. The active adoption of digital channels such as social media, online platforms, and mobile apps allows companies to more accurately segment their audiences, personalize offers, and increase consumer engagement. At the same time, the importance of integrated marketing communications, which ensure consistency across all customer interaction channels, is growing. Despite significant research in services marketing, improving the effectiveness of marketing communications in a dynamically developing market remains understudied. This necessitates further theoretical understanding and practical analysis of the mechanisms behind the use of communication tools in the services sector.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Marketing communications in the services sector have been extensively explored in the works of both foreign and domestic researchers. The theoretical foundations of services marketing and communications policy were laid by Philip Kotler, who viewed marketing communications as a key element of the marketing mix, ensuring effective interaction between a company and consumers [1]. His works emphasized the importance of integrating various communication channels to achieve a synergistic effect. Valerie Zeithaml, Mary Jo Bitner, and Christopher Lovelock made significant contributions to the development of services marketing theory, emphasizing the specific characteristics of services, such as intangibility, inseparability from their source, variability, and non-permanence [2]. The authors note that these characteristics require specific approaches to developing a communications strategy aimed at reducing uncertainty and increasing consumer trust.

The concept of integrated marketing communications was further developed by Don Schultz, who substantiated the need to coordinate all communication channels to create a unified brand information space [3]. His work emphasizes that message consistency contributes to increased effectiveness in reaching target audiences and the development of a sustainable company image.

In recent years, considerable attention has been paid to the impact of digital technologies on the development of marketing communications. For example, Dave Chaffee views digital marketing as a key factor in transforming consumer interactions, providing new opportunities for personalization and analyzing customer behavior [4]. Similar approaches are reflected in the research of Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, who emphasize the role of digital channels in shaping customer experience and increasing loyalty [5].

Domestic and regional studies also confirm the importance of marketing communications for the development of the service sector. Contemporary economists note that effective communications policies contribute to the competitiveness of enterprises, especially in emerging markets, including the economy of Uzbekistan. Particular attention is paid to adapting international experience to national circumstances and the level of digitalization. Despite the significant volume of scientific research, a number of aspects remain underdeveloped. In particular, a more in-depth analysis of the effectiveness of integrated marketing communications in the context of digital transformation is needed, as well as the development of practical recommendations for their application in the services sector, taking into account regional specifics. This underscores the relevance of further research in this area.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To achieve the article's objectives and solve the stated tasks, a combination of theoretical and empirical research methods was used to provide a comprehensive analysis of modern sales logistics models in the service sector. The primary approach was a systematic study of logistics processes through the lens of marketing aspects and customer value. As a theoretical basis, methods of analysis, synthesis, and generalization of scientific publications were used to identify key trends in the development of sales logistics, integration with marketing tools, and the digitalization of service processes. A literature review identified the main sales logistics models (centralized, decentralized, digital, integrated, and adaptive), their functional characteristics, and their role in increasing customer value.

For the empirical portion of the study, comparative analysis and case studies were used to evaluate the practical application of modern sales logistics models in various service sectors. Data was collected through open sources, company reports, statistical materials, and publications by industry analysts. This approach enabled the identification of relationships between the applied logistics model, marketing strategy, and customer satisfaction, loyalty, and competitiveness indicators. The integrated application of the above methods ensured the scientific validity and practical significance of the study's findings, identified areas for improving sales logistics models, and developed recommendations for integrating them with marketing tools to enhance the competitiveness of service organizations in today's environment.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Marketing communications play a key role in the service sector, as they shape consumer perception, trust, and brand loyalty. Unlike goods, services are intangible, the process is inseparable from the manufacturer, their quality is variable, and they cannot be stored, significantly complicating their promotion and requiring a comprehensive approach to communications strategy. Integrated marketing communications combine advertising, PR, direct marketing, personal sales, and digital channels into a single system, increasing the effectiveness of target audience engagement and minimizing information noise. Recent research shows that companies using IMC (Integrated Marketing Communications) achieve higher brand awareness and sustainable competitive advantages in the services market. Digitalization of marketing communications is an important aspect. The use of social media, mobile apps, email marketing, SEO, and content marketing ensures personalized customer interaction, enables audience behavior tracking, database creation, and demand forecasting. Digital tools allow market segmentation, tailoring offers to specific consumer groups, and increasing campaign effectiveness through analytics and direct feedback. In a competitive global environment, digital marketing is becoming an integral element of the strategy of companies operating in the service sector, as it enables them to quickly respond to changes in consumer behavior and market conditions [6].

Marketing communications also play a critical role in shaping the customer experience. Services are directly linked to perceived quality, so communication with customers before, during, and after service delivery impacts overall satisfaction and repeat business. For example, personalized messages, notifications about new products, responses to reviews on social media, and efficient contact center operations increase loyalty and create a positive company image. Research shows that customers who receive consistent, coherent, and informative communications are more likely to become loyal customers and recommend services to others [7].

Branding strategy is particularly important in the service sector. A strong brand not only increases brand awareness but also creates an emotional connection with consumers, building trust and a lasting reputation. Marketing communications aimed at brand promotion include storytelling, expert content creation, PR campaigns, and participation in social initiatives, which is particularly relevant in segments related to the hospitality industry, healthcare, and educational services. International experience shows that a coordinated communications strategy must take into account the cultural, social, and economic characteristics of a region to be maximally effective [8].

In recent years, there has been a trend toward integrating offline and online channels (omnichannel marketing), creating a unified information field for the client and ensuring seamless interaction. This approach provides a deeper understanding of client needs, enables prompt adjustments to offerings, and improves overall satisfaction. The effectiveness of marketing communications in the service sector depends not only on the choice of tools but also on the degree of their integration, personalization, use of analytical data, and flexibility in responding to market changes.

Modern service sector companies are increasingly measuring the effectiveness of marketing communications, as this allows them to evaluate not only promotion costs but also the actual return on investment (ROI). Key performance indicators include the ratio of marketing budget to revenue, the growth in the number of customer touchpoints, and the effectiveness of individual communications tools: digital advertising, social media, email marketing, and SEO. According to an international study, the average marketing budget for companies in the service sector is approximately 9.1% of revenue, and the overall ROI of advertising and communications tools reaches 4.2x, meaning a return of 4.2 times the investment thanks to active communications strategies. Analytics for individual channels show that content marketing can generate an ROI of up to 13x, and email marketing can generate over \$42 in profit for every dollar spent, making it one of the most effective communications tools for services. This level of effectiveness underscores the need for a comprehensive approach to communications policy and regular analysis of its results.

Table 1. Marketing communications effectiveness indicators in the service sector¹

Marketing Communications Tool	Performance indicator (ROI/ result)	Commentary
Average Marketing Budget (% of Revenue)	9,1 %	Services Marketing Budget as a Percentage of Revenue
Total Communications ROI	4,2×	Average Marketing Return on Investment
Content Marketing	13×	ROI for B2B Services
Email Marketing	\$42 for \$1	ROI per Dollar of Spend

¹ Marketing in the Services Industry Statistics: Market Data Report 2026 — основные показатели бюджетов маркетинга и эффективности ROI для коммуникаций в секторе услуг.

SEO Marketing	14,6×	ROI with ~28% of Budget Allocated to SEO
Social Media (Influencer Marketing)	5,8×	ROI for B2C Services
Event Marketing	4:1	ROI of Post-Pandemic Events in Professional Services

These figures confirm that intelligent budget allocation across various communications tools significantly improves the effectiveness of marketing efforts in the services sector. This is especially true for digital channels, which achieve higher levels of customer engagement and better audience behavior analytics. This, in turn, contributes to increased loyalty and a stronger company image.

Marketing communications are therefore an integral element of the competitive strategy of service sector companies. Their effective use increases brand awareness, strengthens customer loyalty, improves the customer experience, and contributes to increased business efficiency. The integration of traditional and digital channels, personalization of messages, and consumer behavior analytics are particularly important. In a dynamic and highly competitive service market, a comprehensive and strategically thought-out communications policy becomes a key factor in sustainable development and growth.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

An analysis of literature, current research, and practical data shows that marketing communications are an integral element of the development strategy of service sector companies. Their effectiveness is determined by the ability to integrate various communication channels, including traditional (advertising, PR, events) and digital tools (social media, email marketing, SEO, content marketing). An integrated approach helps increase brand awareness, build consumer trust, and increase customer loyalty, which is especially important given the intangible and volatile nature of services. Digitalization plays a key role in the transformation of marketing communications. Data analytics and personalized communications provide a deeper understanding of consumer needs, enable tailoring offers to audience segments, and forecast demand. Integration of online and offline channels (omnichannel) enhances the customer experience, ensures continuous interaction, and promotes sustainable business growth.

At the same time, the effectiveness of marketing communications depends on regular monitoring and ROI evaluation, appropriate budget allocation between channels, and the appropriate adaptation of strategies to regional and cultural specifics. Without a systematic approach, even modern digital tools may not deliver the expected results.

While researching the topic, we identified the following problems and expressed our scientific proposals to them, which include:

- developing an integrated marketing communications strategy that aligns all interaction channels to create a unified and consistent information field for the client.
- active use of digital tools (smm, email marketing, content marketing, seo) for personalized engagement with consumers and increased communication effectiveness.
- regular roi monitoring and data analytics enable prompt adjustments to communications campaigns and optimize marketing budget allocation.
- integrating online and offline channels (omnichannel) to ensure a seamless customer experience and increase customer loyalty.
- considering regional specifics and cultural nuances when planning communications campaigns, especially for companies operating in emerging markets.

The implementation of these proposals will enable service sector companies to improve the effectiveness of marketing communications, strengthen their competitive position, create a sustainable image in the market, and ensure long-term relationships with clients.

References:

1. Котлер Ф., Армстронг Г. Основы маркетинга. – Москва: Питер, 2020.
2. Ли Х. Логистика и управление цепями поставок. – Москва: Дело, 2019.
3. Иванова М. Цифровая трансформация логистики в сфере услуг. – Тошкент: Fan, 2021.
4. Петров А. Современные подходы к управлению продажами в сервисной сфере. – Москва: Инфра-М, 2020.
5. Маматкулова Ш. МЕҲНАТ БОЗОРИДА КАДРЛАР СИЁСАТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ БЎЙИЧА МАРКЕТИНГ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАРИНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ //Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 392-397.
6. Ловлок К., Райт Л. Маркетинг услуг. — СПб.: Питер, 2020.
7. Маматкулова Ш. ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ ПО ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ КАДРОВОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА //Экономическое развитие и анализ. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 392-397.
8. Kotler P., Keller K. Marketing Management. — Pearson, 2019.

9. Kumar V., Reinartz W. Customer Loyalty and Lifetime Value. — Harvard Business Review, 2018.
10. Buttle F., Maklan S. Customer Relationship Management. — Routledge, 2020.
11. Mamatkulova S. et al. Improvement of the GIS map of the potential of biomass for the development of bioenergy production in the Republic of Uzbekistan //AIP Conference Proceedings. — AIP Publishing, 2022. — Т. 2432. — №. 1.
12. Mamatkulova S. H. J. Communicative language teaching in the national context. TJE-Tematics Journal of Communication Skills ISSN 2277-3053, Vol-6-(Issue-1-2022), 2-5 [Электронный ресурс].
13. Маматкулова Ш. Ж. Место и роль маркетинговых исследований в маркетинговой деятельности промышленных предприятий //Архивариус. — 2020. — №. 8 (53). — С. 48-51.
14. Блэквелл Р., Миниард П., Энджел Дж. Потребительское поведение. — СПб.: Питер, 2021.
15. Mamatkulova S., Uzakov G. Assessment of the Gross Potential of Local Waste Based on Geoinformation Systems for Bioenergy Production //The Journal of CIEES. — 2021. — Т. 1. — №. 1. — С. 34-39.
16. Mamatkulova S. K. et al. Effect of microbiological biofertilities on cotton fiber quality and expression of genes responsible for trait development //Niva Povolzhia (Niva Povolzhya). — 2022. — Т. 1. — №. 61. — С. 1004.
17. Juraev I. I., Mamatkulova D. J. THE CONCEPT OF INFLATION AND ITS'ESSENTIAL ROLE IN THE ECONOMY // International Scientific and Practical Conference World Science. — ROST, 2017. — Т. 2. — №. 5. — С. 42-43.
18. Jalolovna M. S. Use of modern marketing concepts in the activities of enterprises in the conditions of innovative and digital economy //Web of Discoveries: Journal of Analysis and Inventions. — 2023. — Т. 1. — №. 8. — С. 48-50.
19. Парасураман А., Зейтамл В. Качество обслуживания и удовлетворенность клиентов. — Journal of Marketing Research, 2019.
20. Маматкулова Ш. Ж. 津田梅子の教育思想の特質に関する一考察: 女性の自立と地位向上をめぐる視点から: дис. — Waseda University, 2010.
21. Verhoef P. et al. Omnichannel customer experience. — Journal of Retailing, 2021.
22. Payne A., Frow P. Strategic Customer Management. — Cambridge University Press, 2017.
23. Котлер Ф., Армстронг Г. Основы маркетинга. — М.: Вильямс, 2021.
24. Jalolovna M. S. Quality and Consumer Evaluation of Goods On The Market in an Innovation Economy //International Journal of Scientific Trends. — 2024. — Т. 3. — №. 1. — С. 93-96.
25. Jalolovna M. S. THE ROLE OF CONTENT MARKETING IN ATTRACTING AND RETAINING CUSTOMERS //Western European Journal of Historical Events and Social Science. — 2024. — Т. 2. — №. 3. — С. 22-26.
26. Jalolovna M. S. Features of the development of the marketing strategy of the enterprise //European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine. — 2020. — Т. 7. — №. 2. — С. 6194-6205.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>